

The Dielectric Constant of Binary Mixtures. Part II. Alcohols in Benzene.

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In Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 411) the results of calculation of electric moments and the measurements of dielectric constant of some organic liquids whose molecules do not react upon those of benzene, have been presented and the molecular polarisation has been treated as a function of concentration of the binary mixture, the relationship being given by a linear law. But in the case of associated molecules, this linear law is found not to hold good. It is, therefore, of interest to verify Debye's law experimentally in the case of such molecules. The alcohols have been chosen for the purpose. Besides it has been observed in a previous paper (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1929, 3, 467) that so far as the normal primary alcohols are concerned they have practically the same electric moment, no matter whether the chain is long or short, open or closed. The *iso*-alcohols thus present another interesting point to be studied.

The apparatus used and the method of procedure are exactly the same as described in Part I. The only difference is that very dilute solutions have been used to avoid association of the molecules which generally takes place at higher concentrations. The chemicals used were brought from Kahlbaum. The same formulae have been used. Thus

$$P_A = \frac{P_{AB} - P_B C_B}{C_A} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

and also

$$\begin{aligned} P_A &= \frac{4\pi}{3} N \left(\gamma_A + \frac{\mu^2}{3KT} \right) \\ &= \frac{n_A^2 - 1}{n_A^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M_A}{d_A} + \frac{4\pi}{3} N \cdot \frac{\mu^2}{3KT} \quad \dots \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence μ can be calculated for the solute molecule.

TABLE I.

Solute.	C_A .	d_{AB} .	ϵ_{AB} .	P_{AB} .
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.	0·00	0·872	2·26	26·50
	7·91	0·864	2·58	30·60
	14·72	0·857	2·89	33·97
	16·98	0·854	3·01	35·20
	21·17	0·851	3·16	36·50
	24·76	0·848	3·46	38·96
	32·72	0·842	4·06	43·24
<i>iso</i> Butyl alcohol.	0·00	0·872	2·26	26·50
	3·06	0·868	2·38	28·25
	9·98	0·864	2·40	32·50
	15·30	0·860	2·62	36·24
	19·22	0·855	3·16	38·00
	23·17	0·853	3·38	40·11
	28·72	0·849	3·81	43·85
<i>iso</i> Amyl alcohol.	0·00	0·872	2·26	26·50
	4·38	0·866	2·44	29·25
	7·73	0·864	2·57	31·21
	11·47	0·862	2·72	33·50
	17·10	0·859	2·78	36·95
	22·82	0·853	3·24	40·30
	27·96	0·848	3·44	42·80
<i>n</i> -Undecyl alcohol.	0·00	0·872	2·26	26·46
	1·15	0·869	2·27	26·91
	2·17	0·866	2·32	28·25
	3·34	0·865	2·38	29·77
	5·29	0·864	2·44	31·09
	7·19	0·862	2·53	33·21
	9·62	0·859	2·65	35·85
12·47	0·856	2·74	38·46	
<i>n</i> -Dodecyl alcohol.	0·00	0·872	2·28	26·46
	0·63	0·871	2·23	26·74
	1·32	0·870	2·32	27·89
	2·90	0·868	2·35	29·00
	4·90	0·865	2·41	30·79
	7·56	0·861	2·53	33·99

TABLE I—contd.

Solute.	C_A	d_{AB}	ϵ_{AB}	P_{AB}
n-Dodecyl alcohol	9.98	0.858	2.62	36.28
	13.90	0.858	2.80	4.96
n-Phenylethyl alcohol.	0.00	0.872	2.26	26.46
	1.66	0.878	2.32	27.56
	3.75	0.876	2.50	30.31
	5.44	0.884	2.65	32.28
	7.02	0.886	2.71	33.20
	9.09	0.889	2.80	34.59
	11.48	0.895	2.89	35.87
	13.74	0.898	2.95	36.67
n-Phenylpropyl alcohol.	0.00	0.872	2.26	22.46
	1.00	0.873	2.32	27.50
	2.38	0.876	2.50	29.30
	3.74	0.879	2.53	30.80
	5.20	0.882	2.62	32.22
	6.65	0.885	2.71	33.59
	8.96	0.888	2.80	35.13
	12.27	0.892	2.95	37.60

TABLE II.

Alcohols.	n_A	d_A	P_A	P''_A	P'_A	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
isoPropyl— $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2$	1.377	0.789	83	17.5	65.5	1.78
isoButyl— $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH} \cdot \text{CH}_2(\text{OH})$	1.395	0.806	89	22.0	67.0	1.79
isoAmyl— $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2(\text{OH})$	1.407	0.810	95	26.8	68.2	1.82
n-Undecyl— $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{OH}$.	1.441	0.833	112	55.6	57.4	1.66
n-Dodecyl— $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{OH}$.	1.440	0.830	113	58.9	54.1	1.62
n-Phenylethyl— $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$.	1.526	0.995	93	37.6	55.4	1.64
n-Phenylpropyl— $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$.	1.525	0.990	97	42.1	54.9	1.63

Discussion.

The results clearly indicate that in *iso*-alcohols the carbon atoms associated with the CH-group have different binding forces leading to dipole-moments different in magnitude from those of the primary alcohols. It also seems that μ is larger when the carbon chain is branched as in the *iso*-alcohols. In the case of primary alcohols, the dipole-moment is found to be sensibly constant and the mean value can be taken as 1.63×10^{-18} whereas in the case of *iso*-alcohols, it is 1.80×10^{-18} . This may be presumably explained as follows:—

Hydrocarbons in themselves are non-polar. The introduction of a polar group, such as the OH-radicle in this case, develops a dipole. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that the displacement of the electrical charge which gives rise to the dipole takes place mainly in the radicle itself and in the part of the carbon adjacent to it. This means in turn that the magnitude of the dipole-moment is determined by the nature of the atoms in or near to the OH-group whereas the existence of non-polar groups at a greater distance has practically no effect on the dipole-moment.

Two aliphatic esters have been investigated by Krcbma and Williams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2414). They have used carbon tetrachloride as the non-polar solvent. Their results are—

for methyl acetate, $\mu = 1.67 \times 10^{-18}$

for ethyl acetate, $\mu = 1.74 \times 10^{-18}$.

These two results agree between themselves but are rather different from those obtained for the aromatic esters. They are—

for methyl benzoate, $\mu = 2.06 \times 10^{-18}$

for ethyl benzoate, $\mu = 2.10 \times 10^{-18}$.

Hence the dipole-moment will be considered as a property of the polar OH-group largely independent of the presence of other polar or non-polar groups.

Thus we notice that the dipole-moment is one of the most important properties closely related to the actual electrical structure of the molecules. It may here be remarked that for organic compounds the electrical structure is not so pronounced, and it has been

possible for the chemists to develop an elaborate theory of structural formulae without any consideration of their electrical properties. The electrical nature of inorganic compounds has been considered of primary importance not only from their behaviour in solutions but from various other considerations. It is now more or less certain that the ultimate constituents of matter are the protons and electrons and in organic compounds the forces which bind the different atoms in a molecule should be electrical in origin. The bond theory is still the fundamental basis of organic chemistry. In recent years, however, several electrical theories have been put forward in connection with structure of organic compounds. These theories, as a rule, are not based on electrical properties of the molecules but on their chemical behaviour. The author is of opinion that the dipole-moment of organic molecules can give a clue to the real nature of the bond theory regarding its electrical origin. This, however, will be treated separately elsewhere.

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